

TRIBOLOGICAL BEHAVIOUR OF $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{SiC}_p$ HYBRID METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The tribological behavior of Al_2O_3 fiber and SiC particle reinforced aluminum matrix hybrid composites is investigated under room temperature, 100 °C, and 150 °C in both the dry and lubricant conditions. The effects of fiber orientation and fibers to particles hybrid ratio on the tribological behavior are discussed in details.

Keywords: Tribology, hybrid metal matrix composites, fiber orientation, sliding wear, wear resistance, wear mechanism

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, aluminum metal matrix composites have been well recognized and gradually improved due to their advanced engineering properties, such as the improved wear resistance, low density, specific strength and stiffness. Among all of these superior properties, the improved wear resistance of MMCs has attracted lots of attentions in the field of tribology. In comparison with conventional monolithic alloys, the tribological characteristics of MMCs are improved when reinforcing agents are added to the metal matrices [1]. It was reported that SiC reinforced aluminum matrix composites exhibited higher wear resistance than that of unreinforced aluminum matrix materials [2, 3] and conventional grey cast iron [4]. Thus many researchers have focused on the influences of the agents which are added to reinforce MMCs on their wear behavior. They found that the wear loss was remarkably reduced after hard particles, whiskers or fibers are added. Some of these reinforcing agents are B_4C [1], SiC [1-6], Si [7], TiB_2 [8], Al_2O_3 [9-12], zircon sand [10], SiCrFe and CrFeC [11], and cerium oxide [12]. Having the superior mechanical properties, these composites can be used in high speed rotating and reciprocating elements as wear resistant/friction materials in automobile, aircraft and other applications where the low density of Al MMCs is of great benefit.

The wear resistances of monolithic aluminum alloy (AA6061), its unhybrid composite reinforced with Saffil (Saffil/Al) and SiC_p (SiC_p/Al), and hybrid composites reinforced with Saffil and SiC_p (Saffil/ SiC_p/Al) were investigated by Gurcan and Baker [13]. They found that the unhybrid composites, Saffil/Al and SiC_p/Al , had little advantage over monolithic aluminum alloy. However, the wear resistance of the hybrid composites, Saffil/ SiC_p/Al , was significantly improved over both the monolithic aluminum alloy and unhybrid composites.

The hybrid reinforced aluminium MMCs were also investigated. Fu *et al.* [14] showed that Saffil/SiC/Al hybrid MMCs presented the best wear properties in comparison with

Saffil/Al, Saffil/Al₂O₃/Al, and Saffil/SiC/Al hybrid MMCs under dry sliding wear condition. Under the lubricated condition, the wear properties of Saffil/Al MMCs were the best among them when lubricated by liquid paraffin. Du *et al.* [15] reported that with the increase of the volume percentage of the reinforcement with the 1:1 constant hybrid ratio, the wear value of the composites decreased. And for an equal volume fraction of the reinforcement phase, wear-resistance property of 7A04-matrix composites was better than that of 2A14-matrix composites.

Other researchers focused on the lubricant and high temperature sliding wear. Considering the environmentally adapted oils, mineral oils, and greases containing different amounts of extreme pressure (EP) and anti-wear (AW) additives, the seizure and wear rate testing of wheel-rail contacts were studied by Sundh *et al.* [16]. Liu *et al.* [17] studied the high temperature friction and wear behavior of Al₂O₃ and/or carbon short fiber. They found that the friction coefficient and wear rate of the hybrid composites containing fixed 12 vol. % Al₂O₃ decreased with the increase of carbon fibre volume fraction up to 6 vol. %, and the dominant wear mechanisms shifted to severe adhesion at test temperatures above the critical transition temperature.

From the above discussion, it is found that MMCs have been studied from different points of view to examine the effects of applied load, sliding speed and distance, volume fraction of reinforcements, temperature, size and shape of reinforcing materials, test condition, heat treatment, etc., on their wear properties. However, the effect of fiber orientation and ratio of volume fractions (hybrid ratio) of two reinforcing materials in hybrid composites on the wear properties are hardly found in the literature. The effect of fiber orientation on dry sliding friction and wear properties has been discussed only for Al₂O₃/C/Al hybrid composites in Ref. [18] in which both the reinforcing materials were in the form of short fibers, and in Ref. [19] for Saffil/Al unhybrid composites. However, the effect of hybrid ratio was not taken into consideration. Thus, a detail and systematic investigation of the effects of fiber orientation and hybrid ratio on wear behaviors of hybrid MMCs are imperative. Therefore, in the present study, attention is paid to the investigation of the effects of fiber orientation and hybrid ratio on room and elevated temperature sliding wear behaviors of Al₂O_{3f} and SiC_p reinforced aluminum matrix hybrid composites under both the dry and lubricant conditions. Two different orientations of fibers and three different hybrid ratios were taken into account for the investigation. Further, microhardness tests and SEM images of the worn surface were analyzed to understand the modes of wear.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Specimen Preparation

The MMC specimens were prepared by using cast aluminum alloy, A356 Al-Si, as matrix and alumina fibers (Al₂O_{3f}) and silicon carbide particles (SiC_p) as reinforcing materials. The mechanical and physical properties of the reinforcing materials are shown in Table 1. In hybrid MMCs, both the reinforcing materials, Al₂O_{3f} and SiC_p, were used at different proportions. The hybrid ratio of Al₂O_{3f} volume fraction to SiC_p volume fraction is denoted by F_{n₁}P_{n₂}, where F and P indicate fiber and particle, respectively while n₁ and n₂ denote the percentage quantity of fibers and particles, respectively. For unhybrid MMCs, only Al₂O_{3f} were used and their hybrid ratio was

Table 1 Specification of Al₂O_{3f} and SiC_p

Material	Density [g/cm ³]	Diameter [μm]	Length [μm]	Modulus [GPa]	Hardness [kg/mm ²]
Al ₂ O _{3f}	3.3	3.0	150	310	2000
SiC _p	3.2	30	-	410	2800

denoted by Fn₁P0 (n₂ = 0). Three different categories (F0P20, F7P13, and F13P7) of performs along with their hybrid ratios prepared by vacuum extraction method. For each category, the total volume fractions of the reinforcing materials were kept constant at 20 %. These performs were next used to produce ingots by squeeze casting method. The ingots were passed through T6 heat treatment process. The ingots were passed through T6 heat treatment process where they were heated for 4 hours at 540 °C followed by water quenching. Later, they were artificially aged by heating at 155 °C for 4 hours followed by air cooling.

From each category of MMC ingot, pin specimens with two different orientations of fibers, PR-orientation and N-orientation, were prepared. As shown in Fig. 1, specimens with PR-orientation of fibers are obtained when they are cut in such a way that the fibers are aligned parallel to the sliding surface of the specimen. On the other hand, specimens with normal orientation of fibers have fibers aligned in perpendicular direction to the sliding surface of the specimen. The length and diameter of pin specimens were 15 mm and 5 mm, respectively. The steel counter disk of the pin-on-disk friction and wear tester was made of SCM440 and machined to 7 mm height and 30 mm diameter. The surfaces of pin specimens and disk were polished with 800-grit sandpaper and washed by acetone. Then, they were used in the wear testing experiment. The weight loss of the pin specimens and disk due to sliding wear was measured by a precision electronic balance having an accuracy of 0.01 mg.

Figure 2 shows the optical micrographs of sliding surfaces of the pin specimens of hybrid MMCs with hybrid ratio of 2:1 (F13P7). From Fig. 2 (a), it is easily observed that the fibers are lying parallel to the sliding surface of the specimen that ensures that this specimen has PR-orientation of fibers. Figure 2 (b), on the other hand, shows the sliding surface of a specimen with the presence of small black spots instead of long marks. This ensures that the specimen has the N-orientation of fibers.

Fig. 1 Schematic of MMC ingot and pin specimens.

Fig. 2 Optical Micrographs of F13P7 hybrid MMC specimens: (a) PR- orientation of fibers, (b) N-orientation of fibers.

Condition of Experiment

The wear tests were performed by using a pin-on-disk friction and wear tester. Figure 3 shows the rotating steel counter disk of the pin-on-disk friction and wear tester. The pin specimen is held tightly against this rotating steel counter disk with the help of an applied load. In the case of the lubricant wear test, the surface of the steel counter disk was lubricated with engine oil. For both the dry and lubricant sliding wear tests, the steel counter disk was rotated at a constant speed of 570 rpm which was equivalent to the linear speed of 0.36 m/s of the pin specimen. For the dry sliding wear test, three different contact loads of 3, 5, and 8 kgf were considered while the test was run for a total sliding distance of 2500 m for each of the contact load. On the other hand, the lubricant sliding wear tests were carried out under the contact load of 25 kgf only. However, the test was performed for three different sliding distances of 2500 m, 5000 m, and 7500 m for the same contact load of 25 kgf.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microhardness of the Metal Matrix Composites

As the contents of the reinforcements changed in the hybrid MMCs, the microhardness of these composites varied. The microhardness of the matrixes at each 5 different places were measured by VLPK2000 Mitutoyo Hardness Test Machine using 0.1 N loading energy in 30 seconds dwell time, and then the average microhardness was calculated. Figure 4 shows the microhardness of the matrix in composites with different orientations at different hybrid ratio. It is found that fiber orientation has less influence on the microhardness. However, the value of microhardness decreases to half when the volume fraction of SiCp increases to 13%, *i.e.*, the case of F7P13.

Dry and Lubricant Sliding Wear Behavior

Figure 5 illustrates the weight loss as a function of fiber orientation, hybrid ratio, and temperatures. The highest weight loss is caused by dry sliding wear at room temperature. The hybrid N-MMCs show a higher wear resistance than that of hybrid PR-MMCs in the case of dry sliding wear. At an elevated temperature of 100 °C, the wear resistance

Fig. 3 Schematic view of the pin specimen and disk.

Fig. 4 Microhardness of the MMCs at different hybrid ratio.

Fig. 5 Weight loss of composites with PR- and N-orientation of fiber under different temperatures: (a) dry sliding wear, (b) lubricant sliding wear.

of hybrid MMCs showed a decreased wear resistance in both cases of PR- and N-MMC. In general, the wear resistance was improved while the temperature was increased. As known, the elevated temperature of 150 °C could improve the matrix hardness as a function of aging treatment. It was the reasonable explanation that the weight loss of MMCs with PR- and N-orientation of fibers at elevated temperature of 150 °C was lower than that at elevated temperature of 100 °C. For the lubricant sliding wear, the wear resistance is improved by adding more SiC_p for both the PR- and N-MMCs at 100 °C and 150 °C. The lubricant sliding wear resistance of hybrid N-MMCs at 150 °C becomes the worse than that of hybrid PR-MMCs.

The SEM images of worn surfaces of specimens with different hybrid ratios and fiber orientations are shown in Fig. 6 corresponding to the 3 kgf applied load at room temperature. Figures 6(a) and (b) show the worn surfaces of specimens of F20P0 MMCs with PR- and N-orientations of fibers, respectively. It is observed that the worn surface of the specimen with PR-orientation of fibers has more fragmentations on the worn

Fig. 6 SEM images of worn surfaces of MMC specimens with PR- and N-orientations of fibers: (a) F20P0 PR, (b) F20P0 N, (c) F13P7 PR, (d) F13P7 N, (e) F7P13 PR, and (f) F7P13 N.

surface than that with N-orientation of fibers. This is due to the fact that the whole fibers were spalled out from the surface of the specimen with PR-orientation of fibers which causes the fragmentations on the worn surface and causes more weight loss. For N-orientation of fibers, the whole fibers were not pulled out. Rather, only ends of the fibers were worn out causing less weight loss and a relatively smoother surface in which the phenomenon of surface fatigue can be observed easily.

Figures 6(c) and (d) show the worn surfaces of F13P7 hybrid MMC specimens with PR- and N-orientations of fibers, respectively. The comparison of Fig. 6(a) with Fig. 6(c) shows that the F13P7 hybrid MMC specimens have fewer spalling of fibers than that of the F20P0 unhybrid MMC specimens. This is due to the obvious fact that the F13P7 hybrid MMC specimens contain fewer fibers than F20P0 unhybrid MMC specimens as the total volume of reinforcing materials is constant (20%). So, it is more likely that only fewer fibers spall out from the F13P7 MMC specimens with less fiber content. On the other hand, for N-orientation of fibers, the whole longitudinal surfaces of all the fibers are firmly gripped by the matrix and only the ends of the fibers come in contact with the sliding surface during wear. So, the fibers do not spall out, rather they wear out due to abrasion. When silicon carbide particles (SiC_p) are added to MMCs with N-orientation of fibers, they replace some firmly gripped fibers. It is obvious that the silicon carbide particles (SiC_p) at the contact surface are not as firmly gripped as fibers. Therefore, these particles are more likely to spall out during wear. As a result, the surface of F13P7 MMC specimen with N-orientation of fibers shows more fragmentations (Fig. 6(d)) than that of F20P0 MMC specimen (Fig. 6(b)). Figures 6(e) and (f) show the worn surfaces of F7P13 hybrid composite specimens with PR- and N-orientations of fibers, respectively. For PR-orientation of fibers, the further smoother surface was obtained by adding more SiC_p as seen from the comparison of Figs. 6(a) and (e). For N-orientation of fibers, the further addition of SiC_p caused less number of fragmentations than previous F13P7 specimen as seen from the comparison of Figs. 6(d) and (f).

Figure 7 displays the SEM images of the worn surfaces of MMC specimens after room temperature lubricant wear test. The comparison between Figs. 7(a) and (b) reveals that the worn surface of unhybrid MMC specimen with N-orientation of fibers has more plastic deformation zones than that with PR-orientation of fibers. This tells that the lubricant wear resistance of unhybrid MMCs with PR-orientation of fibers is better than that with N-orientation of fibers. Figures 7(c) and (d) represent the worn surfaces of F13P7 hybrid MMC specimens with the addition of 7% SiC_p . The granulation phenomena were observed in the worn surfaces of the F13P7 hybrid MMC specimens with both the PR- and N-orientations of fibers. From the comparison between Figs. 7(a) and (c), we observed that more fibers of F13P7 hybrid composites were damaged than that of F20P0 unhybrid composites. This is due to the obvious fact that the hardness of the SiC particles in F13P7 MMCs is much higher than that of the matrix and the fibers. Thus, fibers and matrix were severely worn. It caused higher weight loss of the F13P7 hybrid MMCs. On the other hand, although SiC_p were added to the MMCs with N-orientation of fibers, the fibers could not be damaged as severely as that of MMCs with PR-orientation of fibers. Therefore, for N-orientation of fibers, the less weight loss was measured. This indicated that the hybrid MMCs with N-orientation of fibers had a better wear resistance than that with PR-orientation of fibers. The worn surfaces of F7P13

Fig. 7 SEM images of worn surfaces of MMC specimens: (a) F20P0 PR, (b) F20P0 N, (c) F13P7 PR, (d) F13P7 N, (e) F7P13 PR, and (f) F7P13 N.

hybrid MMCs with PR- and N-orientations of fibers are shown in Figs. 7(e) and (f), respectively. For PR-orientation of fibers, the surface of the F7P13 MMC specimen was relatively smoother than that of previous F13P7 hybrid MMC specimen as seen from Figs. 7(c) and (e). For N-orientation of fibers, the addition of more SiC_p improved the wear resistance and we observed further smoother surface in comparison with the previous F13P7 specimens as seen from Figs. 7(d) and (f).

Wear Mechanism

Figure 8 clarifies the wear mechanisms of dry sliding wear of MMC specimens with both the PR- and N-orientations of fibers. For F20P0 unhybrid MMCs with PR-orientation of fibers, although the fibers were not totally consumed away by wear, the fibers were pulled out holistically from the matrix due to the adhesive wear that produced coarse grooves on the worn surface and consequently caused higher weight loss as shown in Fig. 8(a). As the sliding continued, the coarse surfaces were plastically deformed, and debris between the worn surfaces played the role as the subsequent

Fig. 8 Wear mechanism: (a) F20P0 PR, (b) F20P0 N, (c) hybrid-PR, (d) hybrid-N.

abrasive particles. All of these contributed to the wear mechanism. On the other hand, only the ends of the fibers in F20P0 unhybrid MMC specimen with N-orientation of fibers were worn out rather than spalling of the fibers as a whole that caused less weight loss and smoother surface. The weight loss of these types of specimens was principally caused by the abrasive wear.

Figures 8(c) and (d) show the wear mechanism of hybrid MMCs with PR- and N-orientations of fibers, respectively. For PR-orientation of fibers, the addition of harder SiC_p reduced the volume of fibers that were prone to spall out. This increased the hardness of pin specimens which, in turn, improved the wear resistance. Furthermore, in this case, some particles which were just below the fibers on the wear surface protected the fibers from spalling out. Fibers were partially worn out instead of being pulled out holistically. In the case of N-orientation, fibers were firmly gripped over the whole length by the matrix and did not spall out. However, addition of SiC_p reduced the volume of firmly gripped fibers and provided with the surface with relatively loosely gripped SiC_p . Thus, with the addition of few SiC_p , more debris was produced during wear which contributed to the abrasive wear behavior substantially. Therefore, the wear resistance of hybrid MMCs containing fewer SiC_p was found to be lower than that of unhybrid MMCs with N-orientation of fibers. The further addition of particles improved the hardness significantly which played the main role in reducing the weight loss and consequently improved the wear resistance.

Finally, it can be concluded that the wear resistance of MMCs reinforced with fibers only was better for N-orientation than PR-orientation of fibers. However, for hybrid MMCs, the wear resistance was better for PR-orientation of fibers and it monotonically improved by adding more and more SiC_p . For normal orientation of fibers, the wear resistance was found to be improving only after adding enough SiC_p .

CONCLUSIONS

The study of dry and lubricant sliding wear behaviors of Al_2O_{3f} and SiC_p reinforced aluminum matrix hybrid composites were investigated under varying temperature, load, and sliding distance. The wear test was carried out by a pin-on-disk friction and wear tester. To investigate the effects of hybrid ratio and fiber orientation on the wear behavior, three different hybrid ratios and two different fiber orientations were considered. The investigation results can be summarized as follows:

1. At room temperature: In the case of dry sliding wear, the wear resistance of F20P0 unhybrid MMCs with N-orientation of fibers is better than that with PR-orientation of fibers. The reverse behavior is observed for hybrid MMCs. For PR-orientation of fibers, the wear resistance was increasing with the addition of SiC_p . However, for N-orientation of fibers, the wear resistance was initially degraded due to the addition of fewer SiC_p , which was next improving by adding more SiC_p . The wear mechanisms of unhybrid MMCs with PR-orientation of fibers were adhesive, plastic deformation, and abrasive while it was predominantly abrasive for hybrid MMCs with PR-orientation of fibers and both the unhybrid and hybrid MMCs with N-orientation of fibers. In the case of lubricant sliding wear, the lubricant film played an important role in reducing

the weight loss and improving the wear resistance. The wear resistance of F20P0 unhybrid MMCs with PR-orientation of fibers was better than that with N-orientation of fibers. The hybrid MMCs exhibited reverse wear behavior. The addition of fewer SiC_p degraded the wear resistance of MMCs with both the PR- and N-orientation of fibers, which was next improved due to the addition of more SiC_p. The wear mechanisms were fiber breakage, subsurface delamination, and particle crushing.

2. At elevated temperature of 100 °C: In the case of single fiber (F20P0) reinforced MMCs dry sliding wear, weight loss of PR-MMCs was mainly caused by adhesive wear. However, the wear resistance of hybrid MMCs showed a decreased wear resistance in both the cases of PR- and N-MMC. In the case of lubricant sliding wear, the lubricant film had the especial function on reducing weight loss and improving the wear behavior of the friction couples. Furthermore, the improved wear resistance was accompanied by increased content of SiC_p for both the cases of PR- and N-orientations of fibers. The weight loss was mainly caused by abrasive and adhesive wear.
3. At elevated temperature of 150 °C: In general, the wear resistance was improved while the temperature was increased. In the case of dry sliding wear, the trend of weight loss of MMCs with PR-orientation of fibers was increased with the content of SiC_p increased. However, for the MMCs with N-orientation of fibers, the result showed a reverse trend of the weight loss. The wear resistance was remarkably improved by the lubricating film. The trend of weight loss was monotonically decreasing for both the cases PR- and N-orientations of fibers.

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